

How NZ Software Companies Are Adapting Work Settings with Changing Times

The supplementary material includes sample interview questions and the demographics information of the participants and their companies

Sample Interview Questions

Q: What was your team's work setting before the pandemic restrictions?

Q: How did it change during the pandemic?

Q: What is your/ team's work setting after the pandemic restrictions?

Q: Have you moved back to your previous work setting? Why not?

Q: How has your organization adjusted the workplace after the pandemic restrictions to continue flexibility while maintaining productivity?

Companies and Participants Demographics

Company #	Size (NZ)	Product Domain	Participant #	Age	Gender	Role
C1	M	Retail	P1	50+	W	Tester
C2	L	Banking	P2	35-40	M	Developer
C3	L	Accounting	P3	25-30	W	Developer
C4	M	Insurance	P4	35-40	W	Tester
C5	S	Cloud Services	P5	39-35	W	Tester
C6	S	Insurance	P6	35-40	M	Product Owner
C7	S	Health Care	P7	35-40	M	Developer
C8	S	Embedded Systems	P8	35-40	M	Software Engineer
C9	M	POS & Inventory	P9	25-30	W	Senior Software Engineer
C10	S	Health Care	P10	35-40	M	Integration Engineer
C11	L	Finance	P11	30-35	M	Senior Technical Analyst
C12	L	Banking	P12	30-35	M	Product Owner
C13	S	Productivity	P13	35-40	W	CEO
"	"	"	P14	25-30	W	Data Scientist

Company Size (# of employees in NZ): Small (# of employees < 100), Medium (# of employees between 100 and 499), Large (# of employees > 500)